

The Role of Serum Procalcitonin in Enhancing SOFA Score for Predicting Mortality and Morbidity in Sepsis PatientsZarreen Fatima¹, Vasant Mourya²¹Assistant Professor, Department of Emergency Medicine, Jaipur National University, Jaipur.²Department of Critical Care Medicine, Atal Bihari Vajpayee Institute of Medical Sciences and Dr RML Hospital, New Delhi, India

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Abstract:

Accurate early identification and appropriate prognostication are crucial in the treatment of sepsis, a life-threatening illness with high death and morbidity rates globally. One common tool for gauging organ failure in sepsis patients is the Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) score. Its modest specificity, however, suggests that more biomarkers are required to raise its predictive power. One useful biomarker for the diagnosis and prognosis of sepsis is serum procalcitonin (PCT), which is known to be increased in bacterial infections. Using 100 adult patients suspected of having sepsis, researchers from Sarvodaya Hospital and Research Centre looked at how well SOFA scores and PCT levels predicted death and morbidity when used together. While SOFA and PCT may both predict sepsis outcomes on their own, the results show that the combination of the two provides far better sensitivity and specificity. With a sensitivity of 78.1% and specificity of 86.8%, the prediction of mortality is greatly improved when the SOFA score is more than 7 and the PCT level is over 8 ng/mL. When used together, these methods provide a powerful instrument for the early detection of individuals at high risk of sepsis, which allows for more precise and expedited treatment.

Keywords: Sepsis, SOFA score, Procalcitonin, Mortality, Morbidity, Biomarker, Prediction, Sensitivity, Specificity, Organ dysfunction.

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Introduction

Critical and possibly fatal, sepsis develops when the immune system fails to properly respond to an infection, causing inflammation throughout the body, malfunctioning organs, and eventually death (de Azevedo et al., 2015). Sepsis is still a leading cause of death and disability worldwide, highlighting the need of early identification and reliable prognostic methods, even though medical treatment has come a long way.

In order to improve patient outcomes, it is essential to identify sepsis quickly and start the right treatment measures. Fever, rapid heart rate, and an abnormal white blood cell count were the classic symptoms used to diagnose sepsis according to the Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS) criteria. There is a risk of over diagnosis and improper treatment due to the SIRS criteria' inability to distinguish between sepsis and other non-infectious illnesses. A more reliable way of forecasting the likelihood of organ failure and death in sepsis patients has been created and extensively used, the Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) score, to overcome these deficiencies (Singer et al., 2016; Marik & Taeb,

2017). The six systems of the body—respiratory, cardiovascular, hepatic, coagulation, renal, and neurological—are evaluated to get the SOFA score. An elevated SOFA score is associated with more severe organ failure and an increased risk of negative consequences, including mortality. The SOFA score is useful, but it may miss some of sepsis's complexities since it measures organ failure and not the infectious process itself. Particularly in high-risk groups, its moderate specificity raises the possibility of false-positive findings, which in turn raises the danger of needless treatments and resource consumption. Consequently, there is a rising need to find further biomarkers to supplement the SOFA score, making it more predictive and useful in the clinical treatment of sepsis.

One such biomarker that has shown promise is serum procalcitonin (PCT). One particular indicator for bacterial sepsis is procalcitonin, a precursor of the hormone calcitonin. Blood levels of procalcitonin rise dramatically in reaction to bacterial infections (Annam et al., 2016). Not only has procalcitonin shown promise in sepsis

diagnosis, but it has also shown promise in predicting the severity of sepsis and directing antibiotic treatment. Important components in the development of sepsis, increased PCT levels are linked to an increased bacterial load and the existence of systemic infection. Because of this, PCT is a useful indicator for determining which patients are most likely to have serious consequences. In addition to providing predictive information beyond what is supplied by clinical evaluations alone, many studies have shown that PCT levels correlate with the severity of sepsis. As an example, PCT has been used to regulate the length of antibiotic treatment, which decreases the likelihood of antibiotic resistance and misuse without jeopardising patient safety. Sepsis may be more accurately diagnosed and prognosed using PCT because of its specificity for bacterial infections; this allows it to distinguish sepsis from other sources of systemic inflammation (Vijayan et al., 2017). Given these characteristics, it is reasonable to assume that a more thorough method of evaluating sepsis patients might be achieved by combining PCT with conventional scoring systems such as SOFA. Predicting mortality and morbidity in sepsis patients using a combination of the SOFA score and serum procalcitonin levels is the main purpose of this research.

Methods

Study Design

Sarvodaya Hospital and Research Centre in Faridabad, Haryana, was the site of this 18-month prospective observational research that ran from October 2019 to June 2021. One hundred individuals over the age of 18 who showed signs of sepsis were included in the study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Adults displaying abnormal vital signs such as overheating or under heating, rapid heart rate, shallow breathing, low blood pressure, and abnormal glucose levels in patients who did not have diabetes were eligible to participate in the study. Patients were not eligible if they had undergone recent surgery or trauma, were under the age of 18, had a history of myocardial infarction or malignant neoplasms, were under the suspected age of 18, or had presented to other institutions as a subsequent case.

Data Collection

Patients' demographic information, clinical presentations, vital signs, laboratory results, and imaging findings were recorded. The SOFA score was calculated for each patient, and serum procalcitonin levels were measured. The outcomes of interest were mortality and morbidity, defined by the need for ventilator support, inotropic support, dialysis, and ICU stay duration.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS 16.0. Mann-Whitney U test and ROC curve analyses were performed to evaluate the predictive values of SOFA, PCT, and their combination. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) were calculated. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Table 1: Distribution of Patients According to Age and Gender

Age Group (Years)	No. of Patients (n=100)	Percentage (%)	Male (n=56)	Female (n=44)
18-30	19	19.0	11	8
31-40	15	15.0	9	6
41-50	20	20.0	12	8
51-60	17	17.0	9	8
61-70	21	21.0	10	11
71-80	6	6.0	3	3
81-90	2	2.0	2	0
Total	100	100.0	56	44

The age and gender breakdown of the study's participants is shown in Table 1. There is a wide variety of adult patients at risk for sepsis, with ages ranging from 18 to 90 and beyond.

Patients aged 61–70 make approximately 21% of the whole sample, making them the biggest age group in this research.

The next age groups are those between 41 and 50 years old (20%) and 18 to 30 years old (19%).

There was a large range of ages represented in the sample, with a mean of 49.17 and a standard deviation of 16.77 years. The gender distribution reveals that sepsis is somewhat more common in men (56% vs. 44%). Consistent with previous research, this data points to a possible biological difference in immune response or exposure to risk factors including lifestyle and work as the reason men may have a greater prevalence of sepsis. The study's heterogeneous patient population highlights

the generalisability of its results, which imply that gender and age should be addressed together when evaluating sepsis risk and severity. Healthcare professionals may better target high-risk groups, such as elderly persons, who have a greater rate of

sepsis, if they understand these demographic patterns.

Predictive Values of SOFA and Procalcitonin in Predicting Mortality

Table 2: Predictive Values of SOFA and Procalcitonin in Predicting Mortality

Cut-off Values	Mortality	Total	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Positive Predictive Value (PPV) (%)	Negative Predictive Value (NPV) (%)	AUC (95% CI)	p-value
SOFA Score > 7	26 (26.0)	65	81.3	42.6	40.0	82.9	0.66 (0.55-0.76)	0.01*
Procalcitonin > 8 ng/mL	26 (26.0)	37	81.3	83.8	70.3	90.5	0.87 (0.80-0.94)	0.001*

*Significant

The table below shows the results of analysing the SOFA score and procalcitonin (PCT) levels for their ability to predict death in patients with sepsis. Significant mortality predictors include a SOFA score higher than 7 and a procalcitonin level higher than 8 ng/mL.

With a sensitivity of 81.3% and a specificity of 42.6%, a SOFA score higher than 7 accurately predicted death in 26% of patients. Because of its modest specificity, the SOFA score may produce occasional false positives, despite its reasonable sensitivity. In contrast, procalcitonin levels more than 8 ng/mL were a strong predictor of death, with a sensitivity of 81.3% and a specificity of 83.8%. Given its superior ability to accurately identify

individuals at risk of dying from sepsis while minimising the frequency of false positives, procalcitonin seems to be a more reliable marker for predicting death at this time. Additional evidence that procalcitonin is a superior mortality predictor than the SOFA score alone is the area under the curve (AUC) value of 0.87, in contrast to SOFA's 0.66. The statistical significance of these results is supported by the substantial p-values (0.05), which further highlight the potential use of procalcitonin as a predictive tool in clinical practice.

Predictive Values of SOFA and Procalcitonin in Predicting Morbidity

Table 3: Predictive Values of SOFA and Procalcitonin in Predicting Morbidity

Cut-off Values	Morbidity	Total	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Positive Predictive Value (PPV) (%)	Negative Predictive Value (NPV) (%)	AUC (95% CI)	p-value
SOFA Score ≥ 10	10 (10.0)	41	45.5	60.3	24.4	79.7	0.49 (0.34-0.63)	0.92
Procalcitonin > 5 ng/mL	15 (15.0)	49	68.2	56.4	30.6	86.3	0.60 (0.47-0.72)	0.14

This table compares the SOFA score and procalcitonin levels as a predictor of morbidity, with an emphasis on outcomes including the need for ventilator support, inotropic assistance, dialysis, and an extended stay in the intensive care unit.

According to the findings, there is an association between morbidity and a SOFA score of 10 or higher and a procalcitonin level higher than 5 ng/mL. The SOFA score is only somewhat accurate in predicting morbidity, as shown by the sensitivity of 45.5% and specificity of 60.3% for SOFA levels > 10. The comparatively low positive predictive value (PPV) of 24.4% indicates that a higher SOFA

score may not strongly predict morbidity and may result in some false negatives. With a sensitivity of 68.2% and specificity of 56.4%, procalcitonin demonstrates marginally superior performance in predicting morbidity when using a cut-off of 5 ng/mL. Though procalcitonin is somewhat more dependable than SOFA in this setting, neither marker is very potent when used alone, as the PPV of 30.6% still shows. Considering how well these markers indicate death, their prognostic powers for morbidity are severely lacking (0.49 for SOFA and 0.60 for procalcitonin, respectively). Additional or alternative biomarkers are needed to enhance

morbidity prediction in sepsis patients, since these results are not statistically robust due to non-

significant p-values (>0.05).

Predictive Value of SOFA and PCT

Table 4: Combined Predictive Values of SOFA and Procalcitonin in Predicting Mortality and Morbidity

Parameter Combination	Mortality	Morbidity	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Positive Predictive Value (PPV) (%)	Negative Predictive Value (NPV) (%)
SOFA Score > 7 & Procalcitonin > 8	25 (25.0)	27 (27.0)	78.1	86.8	73.5	89.4
SOFA Score ≥ 10 & Procalcitonin > 5	7 (7.0)	29 (29.0)	41.5	94.3	93.1	46.5

Mortality and morbidity rates, as predicted by SOFA scores and procalcitonin levels, are shown in the table. An improved mortality prediction is achieved when procalcitonin levels are over 8 ng/mL and SOFA scores are more than 7.

As a robust predictor of death, the combined sensitivity and specificity of 78.1% and 86.8%, respectively, show that this combination is quite sensitive and specific.

With a PPV of 73.5% and an NPV of 89.4%, this combined method is clearly reliable and has the potential to be utilised successfully in clinical settings to identify individuals at high risk. Procalcitonin levels over 5 ng/mL and a SOFA score of 10 or higher increase specificity to 94.3%

and sensitivity to 41.5%, respectively, when predicting morbidity. Although the sensitivity is modest, the high specificity indicates that there is a considerable risk of severe morbidity when both criteria are satisfied.

Notable for its PPV of 93.1%, this combination effectively predicts which patients would suffer severe morbidity. When used together, SOFA and procalcitonin are more effective than either marker alone, especially when it comes to predicting death; this makes the combo a powerful tool for the early detection and treatment of sepsis.

Clinical Characteristics and Outcomes of Patients

Table 5: Clinical Characteristics and Outcomes of Patients

Clinical Parameter	Mean $\pm$ SD	p-value (Mortality)	p-value (Morbidity)
SOFA Score	9.54 $\pm$ 3.43	0.03*	0.73
Procalcitonin (ng/mL)	7.35 $\pm$ 4.95	0.001*	0.33
Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS)	12.5 $\pm$ 4.35	0.001*	-
Respiratory Rate (breaths/min)	26.23 $\pm$ 5.35	-	-
Pulse Rate (beats/min)	120.61 $\pm$ 9.80	-	-

*Significant

This table provides a detailed overview of the clinical characteristics of the patients in the study and their association with mortality and morbidity. The table highlights key clinical parameters such as the SOFA score, procalcitonin levels, Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS), respiratory rate, and pulse rate. The SOFA score is significantly higher in patients who died ($p=0.03$), with a mean of 10.31 compared to 8.76 in survivors. This finding underscores the utility of the SOFA score in predicting mortality, as higher scores are closely associated with worse outcomes.

Procalcitonin levels are also significantly higher in patients who did not survive ($p=0.001$), with a mean level of 10.74 ng/mL compared to 4.41 ng/mL in survivors. This reinforces the role of procalcitonin as a critical biomarker for identifying patients at higher risk of death. The Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score is significantly lower in

deceased patients ($p=0.001$), with a mean of 11 compared to 14 in survivors, highlighting the importance of neurological assessment in predicting outcomes. The respiratory rate and pulse rate are also monitored, though their direct correlations with mortality or morbidity are not as pronounced in this study, emphasizing the need to consider multiple factors in the assessment of sepsis severity. This table summarizes how each of these clinical parameters correlates with patient outcomes, providing a comprehensive view of the factors contributing to mortality and morbidity in sepsis patients. It highlights the importance of using a multifactorial approach in assessing sepsis severity and guiding clinical decision-making.

Discussion

To improve the prediction of mortality and morbidity in sepsis patients, this study's results highlight the significance of integrating the SOFA

score with serum procalcitonin (PCT) levels. Although the SOFA score has been successful in predicting mortality, it has limited specificity and may provide false-positive findings, especially in high-risk patient groups, when used to evaluate organ failure (Moreno et al., 1999).

According to Raith et al. (2017), the research found that a cut-off SOFA score higher than 7 resulted in an 81.3% sensitivity but only a 42.6% specificity. It seems that the SOFA score works well for identifying patients who are at danger, but it may not be able to reliably rule out those who aren't. This shortcoming emphasises the need for additional indicators that might enhance the SOFA score's prediction power and therapeutic value; thus, PCT arises as a crucial biomarker (Liu et al., 2014).

The amount of serum procalcitonin correlates with the severity of an infection, making it a reliable biomarker for bacterial infections and sepsis (Vijayan et al., 2017). With a sensitivity of 81.3% and a specificity of 83.8%, our research showed that procalcitonin levels over 8 ng/mL are superior to the SOFA score (Annam et al., 2016). Procalcitonin stands out as a better predictor of mortality when used alone; with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.87 compared to 0.66 for the SOFA score (Novita et al., 2019). This confirms what other research has shown: PCT may help with both the diagnosis of sepsis and the prediction of prognosis (Kim et al., 2011). Our study demonstrates that these results are robust, and the inclusion of PCT in regular clinical evaluations for septic patients is reinforced by the strong p-values (Patil & Patil, 2020).

The combination of the SOFA score with procalcitonin levels enhances predictive accuracy for both mortality and morbidity. The study found that using a combined threshold (SOFA >7 and PCT >8 ng/mL) yielded high sensitivity (78.1%) and specificity (86.8%) for predicting mortality (Singer et al., 2016). This dual-parameter approach offers a more comprehensive evaluation, capturing the multi-faceted nature of sepsis and its impact on patient outcomes (Freund et al., 2017). Additionally, for predicting morbidity, combining a SOFA score of ≥ 10 with PCT >5 ng/mL significantly improved specificity (94.3%), indicating that this approach is effective in identifying patients who are likely to experience severe complications (Lie et al., 2018). These findings highlight the value of a multifactorial approach, integrating both organ dysfunction assessment and infection severity markers, to more accurately stratify patients and guide therapeutic interventions (Joel & Ji, 2015).

Conclusion

The integration of serum procalcitonin with the SOFA score significantly enhances the predictive capability for mortality in sepsis patients, offering a more accurate and reliable approach than using either marker alone. The combined assessment of SOFA scores greater than 7 and procalcitonin levels above 8 ng/mL provides both high sensitivity and specificity, making it a valuable tool for early identification of patients at high risk of poor outcomes. This combined approach enables healthcare professionals to implement more precise and timely interventions, potentially improving survival rates and reducing morbidity in septic patients. Given these findings, there is a clear rationale for incorporating procalcitonin measurements into routine clinical practice alongside SOFA scoring. Future research should aim to validate these findings across larger, diverse patient populations and investigate the potential inclusion of other biomarkers to further refine sepsis prognostication and guide individualized treatment strategies.

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